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Abstract

The deliverable "Report on integration of archaeological data in IPERION HS platforms, based on case studies" presents the results of test cases selected among the consortium partners to demonstrate cross-platform integration, addressing archaeological areas such as developments of ancient technologies, investigating dietary habits, movement of goods and people across time and space, and studying materiality, technique and style.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
HS	Heritage Science
MAXRF	Scanning X-Ray fluorescence
RIS	Reflectance Imaging Spectroscopy
LIS	Luminescence Imaging Spectroscopy
THz	Terahertz Imaging
SIRT	Thermography Imaging
OCT	Optical Coherence Tomography
SQL	Structured Query Language
ICOM	International Council of Museums
CIDOC CRM	International Committee for Documentation of ICOM-Conceptual Reference Model

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction

As scientific data and collections documentation regarding archaeological material is growing rapidly, instruments, workflow and methods for the integration of multi-modal and multi-scale data needs to be developed. The importance of such issue is visible through two other European highly interdisciplinary projects, ARIADNE+ and 4CH. Here we present a case study of point level integration of multi-modal and multi-scale archaeological data from a mural painting in of the UNESCO churches of the Troodos Mountains in Cyprus, and a 16th century icon from Deryneia church in Cyprus.

2. Core text

The first case study used for a point analysis level integration is a mural painting (Fig.1) located on the north side of the southwest pier of the church dedicated to Saint Herakleidios in the monastery complex of Agios Ioannis Lambadistis (St John Lambadistis) located in the village of Kalopanagiotis, in the Troodos mountains, Cyprus. The walls within the church are entirely painted, and the scene were dated from the 11th to the 14th century [1], [2], and the monastery complex was granted World Cultural Heritage status by UNESCO in 2001, emphasizing its importance and value.

A MOLAB mission conducted in the end of April and beginning of May with the cooperation of the Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France (C2RMF) and the Laboratoire de Recherche de Monument Historique (LRMH) allowed to acquire a wide range of data of different modalities and different scales, with different purposes. The materiality of the painted artwork was investigated and its spatial distribution was visualized by means of scanning X-Ray fluorescence (MAXRF), Reflectance Imaging Spectroscopy (RIS) and Luminescence Imaging Spectroscopy (LIS). These data were obtained by the means of the MITHRA scanner [3], [4] which is a particularly well-suited and innovative instrument for the point integration of such data as it allows a simultaneous acquisition of the described techniques. The structural organisation in term of the stratified object is investigate by means of Terahertz Imaging (THz). The conservation state diagnostic, inferred from the presence of air pocket in an otherwise homogeneous material is investigated by means of Thermography imaging (SIRT). The 3D point cloud of this part of the church comes from Light Detection and Ranging system (LIDAR), which is settled in a larger scale object describing the entire monastery complex.

Figure 1: Visible picture of the Northern side of the southwest pier of the Saint Herakleidios church

This information is necessary for conservation purpose, such as assets management or monitoring of the changes that could occur over time.

The 3D point cloud is used as the skeleton on which all the different datacubes are placed. Using python environment and the associated scientific library [5], the different datacubes were aligned by interpolating the 3D coordinates and adding these interpolated coordinates as new attributes to the different datacube, thus referencing the position of each point of the different datacubes into a common reference frame. Doing so, the integration of multi-modal and multi-scale data are integrated at point level (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Figure 2: Left, visible picture of the scanned area of the pier by means of the MITHRA scanner. Right, elemental maps of a) calcium (Ca), b) iron (Fe), c) mercury (Hg), d) lead (Pb), e) potassium (K), f) sulphur (S), g) silicon (S), h) copper (Cu) and i) barium (Ba) generated with MITHRA scanner allowing investigation of the materiality of the mural painting.

Added to these scientific data and all the knowledge generated through the interpretation of the results regarding materiality, knowledge from academic work of art history analysis, *i.e.* identification of the depicted figures, analysis of their clothing, etc [6], [7] from different sources such as books, publication or other is also integrated.

Figure 3: Point level integration of the visible image and different elemental maps onto the 3D point cloud of the studied side of the pier. Innovative workflow allowing interpolation for a precise integration of the different data source was used.

In order to save all these information, a structured file at the HDF5 format was created. The HDF5 format [8] was chosen because of its capacity of storing large sets of data and a wide range of type of data. It allows structuring the stored data following a directory architecture. All the data were saved in a common file, and the structure is presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Directory architecture of the created file gathering

The second case study used for this point analysis level integration is a 16th century dated icon from the Deryneia church, Cyprus (Fig. 5) depicting the birth of Christ.

Within the MOLAB mission described earlier, the MITHRA scanner was used to investigate the materiality of the painted artwork by means of MA-XRF, RIS and LIS, and the layering structure as well as the thickness of the painting layer was investigated by means of THz and Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT). The 3D point cloud of the artefact was created by Photogrammetry. Following the same workflow as for the previous case study, the data from the different sources were aligned onto the point cloud. Once this aligned step was performed, the information obtained from each method was converted into a Geographic Information System (GIS) (Fig. 6) and a database containing all the information was built. This model allows the association of information between the database and the visualization on the map canvas (Fig. 7), and is of great interest as the information relative to each point can be displayed, or a query over the entire model can be visualized through Structured Query Language (SQL) environment (Fig.8).

Figure 5: Deryneia icon depicting the birth of Christ

Figure 6: General image of the GIS model

Figure 7: Association of information from the database and visualization of the point (red dot) on the map canvas

Figure 8: Visualization of the points with a signal of Lead (Pb) superior at 98 counts by means of a SQL query filter.

3. Conclusion

Through case studies, the multi-modal and multi-scale investigation of a mural painting from a UNESCO archaeological monument of Cyprus and 16th century icons, we demonstrated the possibility of integrating different type of data at a point level using innovative instrument and workflows. Such results should be integrated within the nowadays internationally accepted standard of CIDOC CRM ontological model (Fig.9) and newly developed model of Heritage Digital Twin ontology [9].

Figure 8: Mapping to CIDOC-CRM of the different spectroscopy applied onto the Lambadistis Pillar

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